

POLYNUCLEAR AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS. PART V. A NEW ROUTE TO 3:4-BENZFLUORENE DERIVATIVES

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By an extension of the method of Mukherji *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 1202 ; 1953, 18, 1499 ; 1954, 19, 328), syntheses of hitherto-unknown 2-methyl- and 2:4'-dimethyl-3:4-benzfluorenes have been described.

3:4-Benzfluorene ring system, unlike other polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons, has not been studied so extensively from the standpoint of carcinogenic activity (Bachman *et al.*, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1937, B 123, 343, 354). The study of 3:4-benzfluorene and its alkyl derivatives, however, offers some points of interest because of their inhibiting action on the implanted Crokes mouse sarcoma (Haddow and Robinson, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1939, B 127, 277, 280). The literature records a few isolated methods for the synthesis of 3:4-benzfluorene derivatives (Cook *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1913 ; Rapson and Shuttleworth, *ibid.*, 1940, 637 ; Fieser and Joshel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 957). The present communication reports a new route to the various alkyl derivatives of this tetracyclic aromatic hydrocarbon by adopting a facile variation of the general method of Mukherji *et al.* (*loc.cit.*) for building up multi-ringed hydrocarbon systems.

The starting material, 2-allyl-1-indanone (II), was obtained through the interaction of 1-indanone (I) (potassio salt) with allyl iodide in 60% yield. The ketone (II), on being subjected to anhydrous aluminium chloride-catalysed condensation with thiophene-free benzene at 0°-5°, produced 2-[β-methyl-β-(phenyl)-ethyl]-1-indanone (IIIa) in 70% yield. Subsequent reduction of (IIIa) with lithium aluminium hydride in anhydrous ether afforded 2-[β-methyl-β-(phenyl)-ethyl]-1-indanol (IVa) in 90% yield.

The carbinol (IVa) was cyclised with concentrated sulphuric acid at 0° in 60% yield to 2-methyl-1:2:10:11-tetrahydro-3:4-benzfluorene (Va) and/or the spiran (VIa). The possible formation of a spiran such as (VIa) can be rationalised by a consideration of the low nucleophilicity of the aromatic system which allows the reaction to proceed in a non-concerted manner (Stork and Burgstahler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 5068) with the intermediate formation of the more stable carbonium ion.

But from energetic considerations the carbonium ion (A) should be more stable than (B) because the positive charge in (A) is in mesomerism with the benzene ring. This reduces or excludes the formation of spiran (VIa) under this condition. However, no attempt was made to separate the two (Va) and (VIa) (if any), since on dehydrogenation both were expected to give rise to the same aromatic hydrocarbon (VIIa) so long as the hydrindane moiety in the spiran (VIa) remained symmetrical. Dehydrogenation of the above hydro derivative (Va) and/or (VIa) was effected over 30% Pd-C catalyst in 4 hours at 300° - 320° in 65% yield. The resulting hydrocarbon, 2-methyl-3:4-benzfluorene (VIIa) furnished a red picrate.

Similarly anhydrous sulphur-free toluene was allowed to react with 2-allyl-1-indanone (II) in the manner of (IIIa) when the ketone (IIIb) was formed in 90% yield. The *para*-orientation in the product (IIIb) was established by its alkaline permanganate oxidation to a mixture of phthalic acid and terephthalic acid. No trace of *isophthalic* acid could be detected, indicating exclusive *para*-orientation under these conditions. The ketone (IIIb), on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride, produced the corresponding carbinol, *i.e.* 2- $[\beta$ -methyl- β -(*p*-tolyl)-ethyl]-1-indanol (IVb) in 85% yield. The cyclisation of (IVb) with concentrated sulphuric acid at 0° afforded 2:4'-dimethyl-1:2:10:11-tetrahydro-3:4-benzfluorene (Vb) and/or the spiran (VIb), in 65% yield.

The dehydrogenation of the above hydro derivative (Vb and/or VIb) was accomplished over 30% palladium-charcoal catalyst at 300°-320° for 4 hours in 70% yield. The resulting 2:4'-dimethyl-3:4-benzfluorene was characterised through its reddish brown picrate.

E X P E R I M E N T A L *

Indanone-1 (I) was prepared from β -phenylpropionic acid, essentially according to the procedure of Johnson and Glenn (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1092).

2-Allyl-1-indanone (II).—To a cooled solution of potassium (3.8 g.) in *tert.*-butyl alcohol (200 c. c.) (moisture excluded) was added dropwise 1-indanone (12.8 g.) and the mixture left standing overnight. To the orange-coloured solid mass that separated was introduced, gradually and with continual shaking, allyl iodide (18 g.). After waiting for one hour at room temperature, the contents were refluxed for 8 hours and sufficient water was then added to dissolve the potassium iodide formed. The contents were then worked up in the customary manner and the product was obtained as a colorless mobile oil distilling at 140-45°/15 mm. yield 10 g. (60%); η_D^{25} 1.5608. (Found: C, 83.20; H, 6.87. $C_{12}H_{12}O$ requires C, 83.69; H, 7.02%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative after crystallisation from ethyl acetate was obtained as orange-red needles, m.p. 161-62°. (Found: N, 16.3. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4N_4$ requires N, 15.9%).

The *semicarbazone* of the above ketone crystallised from ethanol as colorless needles, m.p. 187-88°. (Found: N, 18.8. $C_{15}H_{13}ON_3$ requires N, 18.33 %).

2-[\beta-Methyl-\beta(phenyl)-ethyl]-1-indanone (IIIa).—To anhydrous thiophene-free benzene (100 c.c.) was introduced with vigorous stirring and efficient cooling (0°-5°) a total of 13 g. of anhydrous aluminium chloride and 2-allyl-1-indanone (II: 8 g.) during 80 minutes. The reaction mixture was stirred for an additional 5 hours at 0°-5° and then decomposed with iced HCl and the hydrolysate was ether-extracted. The solvent was flashed off from the united ether-benzene extracts to leave 8 g. (69%) of a light yellow immobile oil which distilled at 197-200°/8 mm, η_D^{25} 1.5862. (Found: C, 85.93; H, 6.95. $C_{18}H_{18}O$ requires C, 86.36; H, 7.25 %).

The *semicarbazone* was prepared in the usual manner and was crystallised from ethanol as colorless plates, m. p. 162-63°. (Found: N, 13.3. $C_{15}H_{13}ON_3$ requires N, 13.67%).

2-[\beta-Methyl-\beta(phenyl)-ethyl]-1-indanol (IVa).—A solution of the preceding compound (7 g.) in anhydrous ether (25 c.c.) was added to a well-stirred slurry of $LiAlH_4$ (0.54 g.) in anhydrous ether (30 c.c.) at a rate so as to maintain ether at gentle reflux. The resulting mixture was stirred and refluxed for additional 2 hours. After cooling, the contents were treated with iced HCl (50 c.c.) and the organic material was taken up in ether. The removal of the solvent followed by vacuum distillation furnished 6.3 g. (90%) of a colorless oil, b. p. 190-95°/10 mm. (Found: C, 85.45; H, 7.78. $C_{18}H_{20}O$ requires C, 85.67; H, 7.99 %).

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Analyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford.

2-Methyl-1:2:10:11-tetrahydro-3:4-benzfluorene (Va).—Cold H_2SO_4 (d 1.84, 5 c. c.) was introduced dropwise to the above carbinol (5 g.), chilled to 0° , and the contents thoroughly mixed and left for 3 hours at 0° . The reaction mixture was then decomposed with powdered ice (10 g.) and worked up in the customary way, yielding 3 g. (65%) of a colorless viscous oil, b. p. $160-65^\circ/10$ mm. (Found: C, 92.10; H, 7.92. $C_{18}H_{18}$ requires C, 92.26; H, 7.74 %).

2-Methyl-3:4-benzfluorene (VIIa).—Dehydrogenation of the above compound (Va: 2 g.) was accomplished by heating with Pd—C (30%, 0.2 g.) at $300^\circ-320^\circ$ for 4 hours. The organic material was dissolved out in ether and the solvent was flashed off. The residual tan-yellow oily hydrocarbon, after regeneration from its picrate, crystallised from ethanol as cream-coloured flakes, m. p. $95-96^\circ$. (Found: C, 93.45; H, 5.9. $C_{18}H_{14}$ requires C, 93.87; H, 6.13 %).

The *picrate*, prepared in the usual way, was deposited as deep red needles which after two crystallisations from alcohol melted at $109-10^\circ$. (Found: N, 8.79. $C_{24}H_{17}O_7N$ requires N, 9.15 %).

2-[β-Methyl β-(p-tolyl)-ethyl]-1-indanone (IIIb).—To well-stirred anhydrous thiophene-free toluene (100 c. c.) were introduced in lots and alternately anhydrous aluminium chloride (16 g.) and 2-allyl-1-indanone (II: 10 g.) during a total period of 80 minutes. After the addition was complete, the contents were stirred at $0^\circ-5^\circ$ for a further period of 5 hours and then worked up as in the case of (IIIa), yielding 14 g. (90%) of a viscous tan mass, b. p. $238-42^\circ/10$ mm, η_{10}^{18} 1.5841. (Found: C, 86.46; H, 7.83. $C_{19}H_{20}O$ requires C, 86.32; H, 7.63 %).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* of (IIIb) after repeated crystallisations from ethyl acetate was obtained as orange-red needles, m. p. 80° . (Found: N, 12.4. $C_{23}H_{24}O_4N_4$ requires N, 12.61 %).

Oxidation of Ketone (IIIb) with Alkaline Permanganate.—The above ketone (IIIb: 2 g.) was refluxed with alkaline $KMnO_4$ solution (12.5 g. in 250 c. c. of water and 12 pellets of KOH) for about 12 hours when the colour of the permanganate discharged. Manganese dioxide was filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated to a small bulk and then acidified to precipitate out a mixture of phthalic acid and terephthalic acid. Terephthalic acid was converted into its dimethyl ester which after crystallisation melted at 142° (lit. m. p. $141-42^\circ$) which remained undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample.

2-[β-Methyl-β-(p-tolyl)-ethyl]-1-indanol (IVb).—A solution of (IIIb: 7 g.) in anhydrous ether (25 c. c.) was reduced with a suspension of $LiAlH_4$ (0.54 g.) in anhydrous ether (35 c. c.) in the manner of (IIIa). The usual working up of the reaction mixture afforded 6.2 g. (88%) of a viscous oil distilling at $220^\circ/1\frac{1}{2}$ mm. (Found: C, 85.8; H, 8.10. $C_{19}H_{22}O$ requires C, 85.67; H, 8.33 %).

2:4'-Dimethyl-1:2:10:11-tetrahydro-3:4-benzfluorene (Vb).—Cyclisation of the above carbinol (IVb: 5 g.) was accomplished by treatment with H_2SO_4 (d 1.84, 5 c. c.) at 0° for 3 hours. The resulting cherry-brown mixture was worked up in the customary manner. Distillation of the product under vacuum afforded 3 g. (65%) of the hydro derivative (Vb) as a colorless viscous oil, b. p. $195^\circ/15$ mm. (Found: C, 91.9; H, 8.02. $C_{19}H_{20}$ requires C, 91.88; H, 8.12 %).

2:4'-Dimethyl-3:4-benzfluorene (VIIb).—The above hydro derivative (Vb: 2 g.) was treated with 30% Pd—C (0.2 g.) at 300°-320° for 4 hours. The aromatised product was subsequently extracted with dry ether and the solvent removed. The residual hydrocarbon was converted into its picrate and was regenerated therefrom as a solid mass which crystallised from ethanol as colorless leaflets, m.p. 64-65°. (Found: C, 93.60; H, 6.42. $C_{19}H_{16}$ requires C, 93.40; H, 6.60%).

The dark red *picrate* on two crystallisations from ethanol yielded needles, m. p. 96-97°. (Found: N, 9.15. $C_{23}H_{19}O_7N_3$ requires N, 9.20%).

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